

TOP CITED ARTICLE IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING RESEARCH FIELD

**International Journal of Software
Engineering & Applications (IJSEA)**

ISSN : 0975 - 9018 (Online); 0976-2221 (Print)

<http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/ijsea.html>

E-GOVERNMENT MATURITY MODELS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Many maturity models have been used to assess or rank e-government portals. In order to assess electronic services provided to the citizens, an appropriate e-government maturity model should be selected. This paper aims at comparing 25 e-government maturity models to find the similarities and differences between them and also to identify their weaknesses and strengths. Although the maturity models present large similarities between them, our findings show that the features included in those models differ from a maturity model to another. Furthermore, while some maturity models are covering some features and introducing new ones, it seems that others are just ignoring them.

KEYWORDS

E-government, portal, maturity model, comparison, best practices, e-services, maturity stages.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijsea/papers/5314ijsea06.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/vol5.html>

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